

Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of 12-membered dioxadiazamacrocycles derived from α -diketones and 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane

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Abstract : 1 + 1 Cyclocondensation of 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane with α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione or benzil in the presence of Co^{II} or Ni^{II} as template affords complexes of the type [ML(NO₃)₂] [where M = Co, Ni and L = 12-membered N₂O₂ macrocycle]. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, magnetic measurements, IR, electronic and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Cobalt(II) complexes, dioxadiazamacrocycles, electronic spectra, FAB mass spectra, IR spectra, Ni^{II} complexes.

Introduction

Macrocyclic ligands represent a class of compounds of relevant interest in coordination chemistry from different points of view ranging from synthetic to structural and analytical aspects. In particular, the macrocycles with mixed oxygen-nitrogen donor atoms can be used as sensors for cations, anions and molecular scaffolds for materials and biological models¹⁻⁵. Oxa-aza macrocycles are also efficient complexing agents for a variety of transition and heavy metal cations⁶⁻⁸. Chandra *et al.*⁹ have synthesized cobalt(II) complexes with 12-membered N₂O₂ donor macrocyclic ligands derived from dibenzoylmethane and 1,2-di(*o*-aminophenoxy)ethane. Lindoy and coworkers have synthesized N₂O₂ macrocycle derived from 1,5-bis(2-formyl-phenyl)-1,5-dioxapentane and 1,3-diaminopropane¹⁰ and have studied cobalt(II) complexes of 15-membered N₂O₂ macrocycle 1,4-diaza-8,11-dioxo-6,7:12,13-dibenzocyclotetradecane¹¹ and nickel(II) complexes of 3,4:9,10-dibenzo-1,2-diaza-5,8-dioxacyclopentadecane-1,11-diene¹². We report herein the synthesis and characterization of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of 12-membered oxa-azamacrocycles derived from 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione or benzil.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Co(NO₃)₂.6H₂O or Ni(NO₃)₂.6H₂O

with 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and different α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione or benzil in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of 12-membered oxa-azamacrocycles (Scheme 1).

M		R ¹	R ²
Co ^{II} (1a)	Ni ^{II} (1b)	CH ₃	CH ₃
Co ^{II} (2a)	Ni ^{II} (2b)	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅
Co ^{II} (3a)	Ni ^{II} (3b)	CH ₃	C ₃ H ₇
Co ^{II} (4a)	Ni ^{II} (4b)	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅
Co ^{II} (5a)	Ni ^{II} (5b)	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅
Co ^{II} (6a)	Ni ^{II} (6b)	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are green solids which are stable at room temperature but decompose on heating. All the complexes are insoluble in methanol, carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene but are soluble in dimethylsulphoxide. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Molar conductances :

Molar conductances of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of oxa-azamacrocycles are found in the range 57–87 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ (Table 1) which are close to those for 2 : 1 electrolytes^{13,14} suggesting that the coordinated nitrate groups are replaced by the solvent molecules.

Magnetic moments :

The magnetic moments of the complexes are given in Table 1. The μ_{eff} values for Co^{II} complexes are in the range 3.90–4.63 B.M. which correspond to three unpaired

electrons. Higher values may be due to orbital contribution^{15–17}. The μ_{eff} values for Ni^{II} complexes are in the range 2.89–3.09 B.M. and are thus typical of nickel(II) with a triplet ground state¹².

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes exhibit three bands at 7234–7662 (ν₁), 13902–13586 (ν₂) and 22226–22636 cm⁻¹ (ν₃) which may be assigned to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}, ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g} and ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} (P) transitions respectively in an octahedral field¹⁸. Oxa-azamacrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} exhibit bands in the region 9890–11121, 16103–17440 and 26000–28555 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{1g} (F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P) transitions respectively¹⁹. On the basis of these data the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of the macrocycles may be assigned distorted octahedral geometry with D_{4h} symmetry.

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of the macrocyclic complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II}

Sl. no.	Complexes	Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analysis (%) :		μ _{eff} (B.M.)	Molar cond. (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
				Found (Calcd.)			
				M	N ^a		
1a	[Co{(Me) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	243	15.32	7.22	4.01	69
		39		(15.48)	(7.34)		
2a	[Co{(Me)(Et)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	246	14.85	6.98	4.52	65
		44		(14.91)	(7.08)		
3a	[Co{(Me)(Pr)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	255	14.22	6.72	3.90	73
		46		(14.40)	(6.84)		
4a	[Co{(Et) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	273	14.28	6.76	4.38	72
		37		(14.40)	(6.84)		
5a	[Co{(Me)(Ph)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	281	13.23	6.22	4.08	83
		49		(13.31)	(6.32)		
6a	[Co{(Ph) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	250	11.49	5.40	4.63	87
		52		(11.68)	(5.54)		
1b	[Ni{(Me) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	198	15.12	7.24	2.92	87
		40		(15.26)	(7.36)		
2b	[Ni{(Me)(Et)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	270	14.59	7.20	3.01	75
		49		(14.72)	(7.10)		
3b	[Ni{(Me)(Pr)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	225	14.14	6.68	2.89	79
		46		(14.21)	(6.80)		
4b	[Ni{(Et) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	201	14.10	6.72	2.97	57
		50		(14.21)	(6.86)		
5b	[Ni{(Me)(Ph)[12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	232	13.20	6.26	3.03	66
		46		(13.12)	(6.33)		
6b	[Ni{(Ph) ₂ [12]dieneN ₂ O ₂ }(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	273	11.38	5.44	3.09	81
		52		(11.50)	(5.55)		

^aThe N values do not include nitrate nitrogen which is removed on treatment with H₂SO₄ in Kjeldahl's method.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra of the complexes confirm that Schiff base condensation has occurred. It is proved by the absence of amine or carbonyl absorption bands at 1700 cm^{-1} and 3200–3400 cm^{-1} respectively and the presence of strong absorption bands at ~ 1590 – 1620 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})^{20-24}$. An absorption band at 1015–1040 cm^{-1} in all the macrocyclic complexes is assigned to coordinated nitrate and the bands at 1460–1560 cm^{-1} confirm the unidentate coordination mode of the nitrate groups^{25,26}.

FAB mass spectra :

The FAB mass spectra of Co^{II} complexes **2a** and **4a** and Ni^{II} complex **1b** have been recorded using NBA matrix and the m/z values along with relative intensities of various peaks are given in Table 2. The peaks at m/z 136,

Table 2. m/z values and % relative intensity of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes

Compd.			
Fragments ^a	2a	4a	1b
$[\text{M}]^+$	395(22.85%)	409(13.15%)	380(2.7%)
$[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$	396(2.8%)	410(7.14%)	381(44.44%)
$[\text{M}-2\text{NO}_3]^+$	271(14.28%)	285(2.6%)	256(5.5%)
$[\text{L}]^+$	212(5.7%)	226(4.7%)	198(2.6%)
$[\text{L}-\text{CH}_3]^+$	–	–	183(3.8%)
$[\text{L}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5]^+$	183(4.2%)	197(2.6%)	–
$[\text{L}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5-\text{CH}_3]^+$	168(5.7%)	–	–
$[\text{L}-2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5]^+$	–	168(6.4%)	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{NO}_3-\text{CH}_3]^+$	–	–	241(4.1%)
$[\text{M}-2\text{NO}_3-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5]^+$	242(5.8%)	256(4.7%)	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{NO}_3-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5-\text{CH}_3]^+$	227(2.8%)	–	–
$[\text{M}-2\text{NO}_3-2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5]^+$	–	225(7.2%)	–

^aAll fragments are unipositive ions.

137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. All the complexes show peaks corresponding to the molecular ions $[\text{M}]^+$ and $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ and free macrocycles $[\text{L}]^+$ which confirm the formation of the macrocyclic complexes²⁷. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the macrocycles, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycle and their complexes. The fragmentation pattern for the complex **2a** is given in Scheme 2. The complex **2a** exhibits a molecular ion $[\text{M}]^+$ peak at m/z 395 (22.85%) and $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ peak at 396 (2.8%). Fragment **b** is formed due to the loss of two nitrate radicals from the molecular radical cation **a** and appears at m/z 271

(14.28%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex.

[A] In this pathway the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and loss of C_2H_5 and CH_3 groups as radicals from **b** gives peaks at m/z 242 (5.8%) and 227 (2.8%) due to the species **c** and **d** respectively. Loss of cobalt radical from the species **d** finally gives the species **g**, m/z 168 (5.7%).

[B] In this pathway the cobalt radical may be lost from the complex in the beginning and a peak at m/z 212 (5.7%) appears due to the free macrocycle **e**. Subsequent loss of C_2H_5 and CH_3 radicals from the macrocycle gives peaks at m/z 183 (4.2%) and 168 (5.7%) due to the species **f** and **g** respectively²⁸.

Antibacterial activity :

The data for the antibacterial activities of the compounds against various bacteria have been recorded in Table 3. The results point out that the compounds are inhibiting the growth of bacteria to a greater extent²⁹. Mode of action of antimicrobials may involve various targets in microorganism e.g. interference with cell wall synthesis, damage to the cytoplasmic membrane as a result of which cell permeability may be altered or they may disorganize the lipoprotein leading to the cell death. According to Lawrence *et al.*³⁰ the variation in toxicity of different antibacterial agents against different organism depends on impermeability of the cell. Such activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of Overtone's concept and Tweedy's chelation theory³¹.

Experimental*Materials :*

$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) were of AR grade. 1,8-Diamino-3,6-dioxacatane (Merck), 2,3-pentanedione (Fluka), 2,3-hexanedione (Merck), 3,4-hexanedione (Aldrich), 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione (Aldrich), 2,3-butanedione (Aldrich), benzil (Sisco Chem), *n*-butanol (Merck) and DMSO were distilled before use.

Analytical methods and physical measurements :

Cobalt and nickel were determined by standard methods³². Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (302 K) on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Co}\{(\text{Me})(\text{Et})[12]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_2\}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

Table 3. Antibacterial screening data of the complexes

Compd.	Inhibition (mm) after 24 h (conc. in ppm)		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (-)	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> (-)	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (-)
1a	15	23	18
2a	9	11	14
3a	11	8	10
4a	18	7	16
5a	12	11	13
6a	21	9	8
1b	7	15	5
2b	10	17	10
3b	13	10	6
4b	6	9	13
5b	13	6	6
6b	19	7	19

as a calibrant. Molar conductances of 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. The IR spectra (KBr) in the region $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 Mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes :

Co^{II} nitrate (0.920 g, 3.16 mmol) was dissolved in ~ 15 mL *n*-butanol and 2,3-butanedione (0.272 g, 3.15 mmol in 15 mL *n*-butanol) was added with stirring. To this, a solution of 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane (0.468 g, 3.15 mmol in 15 mL *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring which was continued for ~ 5 h. The

solid appeared was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly the corresponding Ni^{II} complex was synthesized. Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of other oxa-azamacrocycles derived from 1,8-diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione, 3,4-hexanedione, 1-phenylpropane-1,2-dione or benzil were synthesized by similar procedure.

Antibacterial screening :

Antibacterial activity was evaluated by the paper disc plate method³³. The nutrient agar medium (peptone, beef extract, NaCl and agar-agar) and 5 mm diameter paper discs of Whatman No. 1 filter paper were used. The compounds were dissolved in 500 ppm concentration. The filter paper discs were soaked in different solutions of the compounds, dried and then placed in the petriplates previously seeded with the test organisms. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 30 °C and the inhibition zone around each disc was measured.

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References

- J. M. Lehn, "Supramolecular Chemistry", VCH, New York, 1995.
- L. F. Lindoy, "The chemistry of macrocyclic ligand complexes", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1989.
- G. W. Gokel, W. F. Leevy and M. E. Weber, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 2723.
- K. P. Wainwright, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1997, **35**, 166.
- V. Bernhardt and G. A. Lawrance, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **104**, 297.
- R. M. Izatt, J. S. Bradshaw, S. A. Nielsen, J. D. Lamb and J. J. Christensen, *Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **85**, 271.
- K. E. Krakowiak, J. S. Bradshaw and D. J. Zamecka-Krakowiak, *Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **89**, 929.
- R. M. Izatt, K. Pawlak, J. S. Bradshaw and R. L. Bruening, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 1721.
- S. Chandra and R. Kumar, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Nano Met. Chem.*, 2005, **35**, 161.
- L. G. Armstrong and L. F. Lindoy, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1322.
- L. F. Lindoy, H. C. Lip, J. H. Rea, R. J. Smith, K. Henrich, M. McPartlin and P. A. Tasker, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 3360.
- L. G. Armstrong, P. G. Grimsley, L. F. Lindoy, H. C. Lip, V. A. Norris and R. J. Smith, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 2350.
- J. Lewis, T. D. O. Donoghue and P. R. Raithby, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 1380.
- J. Lewis and T. D. O. Donoghue, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 736.
- M. Gerloch, J. Lewis, F. E. Mabbs and A. Richards, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 112.
- S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 775.
- L. G. Armstrong, L. F. Lindoy, M. McPartlin, G. M. Mockler and P. A. Tasker, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 1665.
- M. R. Reddy, K. M. Raju and H. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 677.
- M. C. Rakowski, M. Rycheck and D. H. Busch, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1194.
- S. M. Nelson, M. McCann, C. Stevenson and M. G. B. Drew, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 1477.
- M. G. B. Drew, A. H. bin Othman, S. G. Mcfall, P. D. A. McIlroy and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1173.
- R. Saraswat, S. Singh and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 478.
- R. Saraswat and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 493.
- V. B. Rana and M. P. Teotia, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 267.
- A. Walken and J. R. Ferraro, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **43**, 2689.
- M. G. B. Drew, A. H. bin Othman, P. D. A. McIlroy and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 250.
- D. H. Cook and D. E. Fenton, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 810.
- Z. A. Siddiqi and M. M. Khan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2004, **34**, 897.
- S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2005, **30**, 630.
- P. G. Lawrence, P. L. Harold and O. G. Francie, *Antibiotic and Chemotherapy*, 1980, **5**, 1597.
- B. G. Tweedy, *Phytopathology*, 1964, **55**, 910.
- A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longman, London, 1961.
- S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 2004, **60**, 1751; W. G. Hanna and M. M. Moaward, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 644.

